

DECOMPOSITION OF HYDROGEN PEROXIDE BY POTASSIUM FERROCYANIDE PART I.

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When a solution of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ is illuminated by bright sunlight, a photochemical equilibrium is set up with the production of potassium aquopentacyanoferrite upto a maximum concentration. This equilibrium has been found to be reversible in the dark. The potassium aquopentacyanoferrite so produced is responsible for the phenomenon of after-effect observed in the decomposition of H_2O_2 by illuminated $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ solution. The aquo-salt is more reactive in the presence of excess of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ than without it. The greater the time of exposure of $K_4Fe(CN)_6-H_2O_2$ mixture the greater is the velocity of decomposition of H_2O_2 , whereas a solution of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ illuminated to sunlight prior to its mixing with H_2O_2 in the dark, decomposes H_2O_2 with the same velocity irrespective of the duration of exposure. Based on these observations a mechanism of this reaction has been outlined.

Kistiakowsky (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1900, **35**, 431) observed that a mixture of H_2O_2 and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and $K_3Fe(CN)_6$, or H_2O_2 and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ exposed to light and then brought back to darkness decomposes with a much higher velocity than a reaction mixture which has not been illuminated. The insolation of the mixture, however short it might be, had the pronounced effect in that the activity continued long after illumination.

A detailed study of the literature on the subject reveals much confusion as regards the cause of enhanced reactivity of the illuminated mixtures of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and H_2O_2 . Kistiakowsky (*loc. cit.*) attributes this marked reactivity to the formation of a catalyser (possibly of a colloidal nature) which continues its active influence after subsequent darkening. Weigert (*Ann. Phys.*, 1907, *iv*, **24**, 243) suggests that insolation produces reaction nuclei which act catalytically. Winther (*Danske. Viden. Medd.*, 1920, **2**, No. 1, 1) explains the phenomenon by assuming gradual formation of an extremely stable substance, which catalytically accelerates the decomposition of H_2O_2 . Rao and Srikantan (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 29), on the other hand, find this reaction to be very complicated and not unimolecular with respect to H_2O_2 , as observed by Kistiakowsky. Amann (*Z. Chem. Ind.-Kolloide*, 1911, **8**, 14) attributes enhanced reactivity in this reaction after illumination to the production of a photo-phase by insolation of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ solution. From the above it is clear that inspite of so many theories, there is hardly any experimental evidence in their support.

In order to elucidate the reaction mechanism, a knowledge of the properties of aqueous solution of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ is necessary, but there is a

difference of opinion on this question. According Matuschek (*Chem. Z.*, 1901, 25, 565) ferric hydroxide is produced by insolating $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ solution. Haber (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1905, 10, 846) and Foster (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 916) suggest the following scheme:—

Baudisch (*Ber.*, 1922, 55, 2701), on the other hand, finds that ferric hydroxide, HCN and OH ions are produced on exposing $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ solution to sunlight. Baur (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1925, 8, 403) observes that ferrocyanide decomposes into ferric hydroxide sol, the hydroxide being later precipitated. This is due to ferricyanide impurity always present in ferrocyanide, which is itself photochemically insensitive. Thus the above authors are inclined to believe that either one, or more of the products Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , and ferric hydroxide sol results from the insolation of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ solution.

Iimori (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 167, 145), however, established by spectroscopic evidence that the absorption spectrum of illuminated solution of the salt is identical with that of potassium aquopentacyanoferrite, and proposed the following mechanism:—

He states that the light reaction is a reversible one.

In order to elucidate the reaction mechanism of illuminated $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and H_2O_2 in the light of the above theories, it was thought best to add Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , and colloidal ferric hydroxide to a mixture of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and H_2O_2 in the dark and study the velocity constant. It was, however, found that colloidal ferric hydroxide, prepared by adding NaOH to ferric chloride and subsequently dialysing it for three months till $AgNO_3$ ceased to show any opalescence with the dialystate, did not accelerate the decomposition of H_2O_2 either in presence or absence of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$. Ferrous and ferric ions could not exist as both these ions should show blue colour with $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ generated by the oxidation of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ by H_2O_2 . Moreover, reactions performed with $N/6-H_2O_2$ and 0.005% solution of ferric chloride (the same concentration as of sodium aquopentacyanoferrite) did not give an appreciable velocity of decomposition of H_2O_2 , both in presence and absence of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$. Ferric ion is thus proved to be of no reactivity so far as this reaction is concerned, at least at the concentration

stated above, and at this concentration $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ with $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ produces considerable activity as shown in the following experiments. Having eliminated all the above possibilities, it was considered desirable to test the hypothesis advanced by Iimori (*loc. cit.*) that $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ on illumination is converted into potassium aquopentacyanoferrite.

EXPERIMENTAL.

For the preparation of sodium aquopentacyanoferrite (as the potassium salt is not easily available) a method proposed by Hofmann (*Annalen*, 1900, **312**, 31) was adopted. Sodium nitroprusside (20 g.) was treated with 10 g. of anhydrous sodium carbonate dissolved in 80 c.c. of water. To this was added 7 g. of hydroxylamine hydrate hydrochloride, dissolved in a little water, cooled with ice. Evolution of gas began immediately and the solution was coloured greenish brown. After one hour the sodium aquo-salt was precipitated with three times the volume of alcohol as a brown gummy mass. By repeated dissolving in water and precipitation with methyl alcohol, the substance was finally obtained as a lemon-yellow powder. The temperature was kept below 5° . The preparation was dried over sulphuric acid at 17 mm. pressure for 48 hours, when yellowish brown aquo-salt of the formula* $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained.

It is clear from the above that if potassium aquopentacyanoferrite is produced by insolation of aqueous solution of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, the former substance should decompose hydrogen peroxide in the dark. In the following experiments, Kahlbaum's pure $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ was used in conductivity water. Pure H_2O_2 was prepared by taking Kahlbaum's pure Na_2O_2 and pure H_2SO_4 and distilling the hydrogen peroxide at 17 mm. pressure in Jena glass apparatus. The distillate gave test for traces of H_2SO_4 , which was possibly mechanically carried over. Hence the distillate was shaken with pure CaCO_3 , filtered and redistilled. In this way pure aqueous H_2O_2 was obtained which was free from chloride and sulphate.

Though the velocity constants obtained here leave something to be desired, they are as good as those reported in the literature (Kistiakowsky, *loc. cit.*, Brédig, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, **31**, 258; 1901, **31**, 3, 323; Brossa, *ibid.*, 1909, **66**, 161; Tartar and Schaffer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 2604). It is necessary to mention here that this reaction is highly

* The iron content was gravimetrically estimated and a variation of 4.0% from the theoretical value was obtained. This may be due to a slight impurity and also to the highly hygroscopic nature of the compound.

susceptible to traces of impurities, for in parallel experiments sometimes there occur errors of more than 20% which cannot be attributed to the errors in manipulation, but can only be accounted for by the impurities in the air of the laboratory. The surface of the reaction vessel also has a disturbing effect. The reactions were carried in the dark room in duly cleaned and steamed Jena glass-stoppered bottles, and 5 c.c. of the reaction mixture were taken out after definite time intervals. $N/20.96\text{-KMnO}_4$ was used to determine the change in concentration of H_2O_2 . The amount of KMnO_4 taken up by $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ was subtracted from the total amount of KMnO_4 used. The strengths of H_2O_2 and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ were $N/6$ and $M/64.2$ respectively. The total volume of the reaction mixture in all the experiments was 50 c.c. $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ and sodium aquopentacyanoferrite solutions were prepared in the dark and kept in black bottles. The reactions were carried out at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in the dark room and unilluminated solutions were always used unless otherwise stated. The reaction is unimolecular with respect to H_2O_2 and therefore

$$K = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}.$$

The amount of KMnO_4 taken up by the ferrite is negligibly small

In the following tables, allowance made for $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ in 5 c.c. of reaction mixture = 1.6 c.c. of $N/20.96\text{-KMnO}_4$.

TABLE I.

25 C.c. of $N/3\text{-H}_2\text{O}_2$ + 25 c.c. of $M/32.10\text{-K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ (0.3242 g.).

Time.	KMnO_4 .	Corr. vol.	$K \times 10^5$.	Time.	KMnO_4 .	Corr. vol.	$K \times 10^5$.
0 min.	17.50 c.c.	15.90	—	261 min.	11.45 c. c.	9.85	80
26	16.80	15.20	76	295	10.60	9.00	84
102	15.00	13.40	73	336	9.30	7.70	94
150	13.95	12.35	73				

TABLE II.

25 C.c. of $N/3\text{-H}_2\text{O}_2$ + 25 c.c. of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.0025 g.).

Time.	KMnO_4 .	$K \times 10^5$.	Time.	KMnO_4 .	$K \times 10^5$.
0 min.	15.90 c. c.	—	111 min.	13.35 c.c.	68
5	15.45	250	160	12.70	61
35	14.50	114	240	11.55	58
61	14.15	83	305	10.85	54

TABLE III.

25 C.c. of $N/3\text{-H}_2\text{O}_2$ + 10 c.c. of $M/25\cdot68\text{-K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ (0·3242 g.) + 10 c.c. of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0·0025 g.) + 5 c.c. of water. $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ was added to H_2O_2 and to this mixture was added the aquo-salt.

Time.	KMnO ₄ .	Corr. vol.	$K \times 10^5$.	Time.	KMnO ₄ .	Corr. vol.	$K \times 10^5$.
0 min.	17·50 c.c.	15·90	—	57·5 min.	3·50 c.c.	1·90	1604
26	7·35	5·75	1699	66	3·05	1·45	1576
34·5	5·90	4·30	1646	81	2·45	0·85	1570
46	4·60	3·00	1575	102	1·95	0·35	1624

TABLE IV.

25 C.c. of $N/3\text{-H}_2\text{O}_2$ + 10 c.c. of $M/25\cdot68\text{-K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ (0·3242 g.) + 2 c.c. of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0·0005 g.) + 13 c.c. of water.

Time.	KMnO ₄ .	Corr. vol.	$K \times 10^5$.	Time.	KMnO ₄ .	Corr. vol.	$K \times 10^5$.
0 min.	17·50 c.c.	15·90	—	68 min.	6·45 c.c.	4·85	758
24·5	11·75	10·15	796	79	5·45	3·85	780
43	9·15	7·55	752	102	4·10	2·50	788
55	7·80	6·20	744	125	3·15	1·55	809

TABLE V.

25 C.c. of $N/3\text{-H}_2\text{O}_2$ + 10 c.c. of $M/25\cdot68\text{-K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ (0·3242 g.) + 0·40 c.c. of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0·0001 g.) + 14·6 c.c. of water.

Time.	KMnO ₄ .	Corr. vol.	$K \times 10^5$.	Time.	KMnO ₄	Corr. vol.	$K \times 10^5$.
0 min	17·50 c.c.	15·90	—	102 min.	10·25 c.c.	8·65	259
27	14·80	13·20	299	125	9·30	7·70	252
41·5	13·55	11·95	299	253	5·30	3·70	250
60	12·50	10·90	273	284	4·50	2·90	260
78	11·60	10·00	258				

TABLE VI.

25 C.c. of $N/3\text{-H}_2\text{O}_2$ + 25 c.c. of $M/32\cdot10\text{-K}_4\text{Fe(CN)}_6$ (0.3242 g.).

A.				B. Exposed to bright sunlight for 2 min. and then at once mixed with H_2O_2 in the dark.			
Time.	KMnO ₄	Corr. vol.	$K \times 10^5$.	Time.	KMnO ₄	Corr. vol.	$K \times 10^5$.
0 min.	16.70 c.c.	15.10	—	0 min	16.55 c.c.	14.95	—
45	15.60	14.00	73	4.5	14.65	13.05	1316
79	14.40	12.80	91	24	9.65	8.05	1120
120	13.30	11.70	92	40	6.65	5.05	1178
187	11.25	9.65	104	50	5.35	3.75	1201
220	10.05	8.45	115	61	4.35	2.75	1206
				74	3.35	1.75	1259
				86	2.70	1.10	1317

TABLE VII.

25 C.c. of $N/3\text{-H}_2\text{O}_2$ + 25 c.c. of $M/32\cdot10\text{-K}_4\text{Fe(CN)}_6$ (0.3242 g.).A. Exposed to bright sunlight in quartz tube for 5 min. then mixed with H_2O_2 at once in the dark room.

B. Exposed in quartz tube to bright sunlight for 5 min. but used after keeping in the dark room for 20 min.

Time.	KMnO ₄	Corr. vol.	$K \times 10^5$.	Time.	KMnO ₄	Corr. vol.	$K \times 10^5$.
0 min.	16.20 c.c.	14.60	—	0 min	16.50 c.c.	14.90	—
12	11.55	9.95	1388	27	16.20	14.60	33
25	8.60	7.06	1277	54	15.40	13.80	62
38	6.45	4.85	1260	180	10.85	9.25	115
50	4.90	3.30	1292	210	10.00	8.40	119
66	4.00	2.40	1188	240	9.20	7.60	122
95	2.85	1.25	1124	270	8.00	6.40	136
				300	7.50	5.90	134

In the control the value of $K \times 10^5$ is 83.

TABLE VIII.

25 C. c. of $N/3 \cdot H_2O_2$ + 25 c. c. of $M/32 \cdot 10 \cdot K_4Fe(CN)_6$ (0.3242 g.).

A.				B.			
Time.	KMnO ₄ .	Corr. vol.	$K \times 10^5$.	Time.	KMnO ₄ .	Corr. vol.	$K \times 10^5$.
0 min.	17.00 c.c.	15.40	—	0 min.	17.05 c.c.	15.45	—
50	15.70	14.10	76	50	15.65	14.05	83
70	9.20	7.60	—	85	4.35	2.70	—
90	5.70	4.10	1340	90	3.60	2.00	2766
106.5	4.10	2.50	1323	100	2.60	1.00	2733
120	3.25	1.65	1326				
150	2.20	0.60	1380				

N.B.—After 50 min the reaction mixtures in Tables A and B were exposed to sunlight for 1 and 5 minutes respectively, and then they were removed to the dark room and the velocity constants measured.

DISCUSSION.

The above data (Tables I, II, III) show that sodium aquopentacyanoferrite enhances the rate of decomposition of H_2O_2 in the dark considerably only when excess of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ is present in the reaction mixture. If the aquo-salt alone is used in the dark without the addition of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, the rate of decomposition is much lower compared to the above reaction velocity (*cf.* Tables II and III).

Another important fact brought out from the data in Tables VI and VII is that the time of insolation of aqueous solution of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, prior to its addition to H_2O_2 in the dark, does not have any effect on the final reaction rate. In other words, insolation of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ for any length of time (2 min. or 5 min.) produces the active substance, potassium aquopentacyanoferrite, upto a maximum concentration and further exposure does not raise its concentration.

Further analysis of the above experimental results revealed the very important fact that if a solution of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ alone is exposed to sunlight and immediately used for the decomposition of H_2O_2 in the dark, the

velocity constant is very much higher and compares well with that obtained with exposed mixture of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and H_2O_2 . If, on the other hand, an illuminated solution of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ is kept in the dark for 10-20 minutes before using, it does not show any increase in the velocity when compared with blanks. But, on the contrary, the initial velocity constants are definitely lower than those obtained in controls, and towards the end of the reaction, the values of the velocity constants approach the values obtained in controls (*cf.* Tables VI and VII).

It is also clear from the data available (Tables III, IV, V) that the greater the amount of sodium aquopentacyanoferrite taken with the same amount of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, the greater is the value of K .

The following mechanisms may be suggested on the evidence adduced from the foregoing experiments:—

i.e., a photochemical equilibrium is established and the reaction is reversible in the dark.

(ii) $K_3Fe(CN)_5 \cdot H_2O$ so produced vigorously decomposes H_2O_2 , as is evident from the violent evolution of oxygen from the mixture. At the same time oxidation of $K_3Fe(CN)_5 \cdot H_2O$ takes place

Potassium aquopentacyanoferrate is produced, which is further reduced as follows:—

In the light of the above mechanism the above mentioned facts are readily explained.

* In an illuminated mixture of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and H_2O_2 , traces of aquopentacyanoferrite also exist and four reactions actually proceed in such a mixture in the dark, resulting in the disappearance of H_2O_2

(i) Decomposition of H_2O_2 by aquopentacyanoferrite generated by illumination of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$.

(ii) Decomposition of H_2O_2 by $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ [The dark reaction which was originally going on in the mixture of H_2O_2 and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ before illumination].

(iii) Reduction of H_2O_2 by aquoferrite.

(iv) Reduction of H_2O_2 by $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$.

Since the evolution of oxygen from an illuminated mixture of H_2O_2 and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ is very vigorous, it is evident that the fast disappearance of H_2O_2 is mainly due to its decomposition and not due to its reduction. Some H_2O_2 is no doubt used up in oxidising the ferrite to ferrate which imparts a violet colour to the reaction mixture not containing $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ (*cf.* Table II). H_2O_2 also oxidises a part of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ to $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$. The velocity of decomposition of H_2O_2 by $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ in the dark (which includes the reactions (ii) and (iv)) is very small compared to the velocity of decomposition of H_2O_2 by illuminated $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$; only a small portion of the total H_2O_2 is so decomposed. The aquo-salt being in very minute amounts, only a very small fraction of the total H_2O_2 present suffers reduction and the rest undergoes rapid catalytic decomposition. During a certain time interval, therefore, the amount of H_2O_2 decomposed by the ferrite is very much more in comparison to the amount of H_2O_2 lost in the reactions (ii), (iii) and (iv). Thus the disturbing effect of the reactions (ii), (iii) and (iv) is small and the values of K are fairly constant, when calculated on the basis of the unimolecular reaction. It is notable that in mixtures of H_2O_2 and aquoferrite, the value of K is not constant, but falls rapidly (*cf.* Table II) because $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ is not there to maintain the concentration of the aquoferrite.

When the aquopentacyanoferrite is used with H_2O_2 without the addition of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, decomposition of H_2O_2 takes place as is evident from the evolution of oxygen, and aquopentacyanoferrate of violet colour is also produced due to oxidation as shown in equation (ii). The violet colour of aquoferrate as described by Hofmann (*loc. cit.*) is actually obtained in the experiment described in Table II. The aquopentacyanoferrite decomposes H_2O_2 very quickly and the ferrate, which is produced due to oxidation, slowly decomposes H_2O_2 towards the latter part of reaction (*cf.* Table II). Thus the change of aquopentacyanoferrite to aquopentacyanoferrate also accounts for a higher value of K in the beginning, and a slower rate towards the later stage, which is due to the slow decomposition of H_2O_2 by the ferrate.

On the other hand, a mixture of H_2O_2 with $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ and a solution of sodium aquopentacyanoferrite gives a very high rate of decomposition, which is maintained at its initial value to the very end of the reaction (Tables III, IV, V). This is explained by the proposed mechanism con-

sidering the equations (ii) and (iii). The aquoferrate once produced reacts immediately with $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and reforms aquoferrite, so that to all intents and purposes, the initial amount of aquoferrite added is always present as such as long as excess of potassium ferrocyanide is there, and this accounts for a uniformly high reaction rate. Also the end-solution is yellow and not violet, which definitely points out that ferrate is not present. The reaction in equation (iii) is very fast compared to the reaction in equation (i).

It is clear from Table VIII that the greater the time of exposure of $K_4Fe(CN)_6 - H_2O_2$ mixture, the greater is the resultant velocity constant, which fact is also in conformity with the suggested reaction mechanism. Since excess of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ is always present in the mixture, potassium aquopentacyanoferrite produced by insolation reacts with H_2O_2 disturbing the equilibrium (i). More of the aquoferrite is, therefore, produced again to maintain the equilibrium and hence on the whole, a greater amount of aquoferrite is produced than would have resulted for the same duration of insolation, if H_2O_2 were not present to remove it by oxidation from the field of reaction. This increased concentration of the aquoferrite increases the decomposition rate considerably according to the data in Tables III, IV and V. As soon as the mixture is removed to the dark room, the reaction goes to the left so that ultimately a definite quantity of potassium aquopentacyanoferrite, depending upon the time of exposure, participates in the reaction. Hence the greater the time of exposure, the greater is the value of K .

That the time of exposure of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ alone, prior to mixing with H_2O_2 in the dark, has no particular effect on the final result is also accounted for by the existence of an equilibrium as shown in equation (i). It has been seen (Tables III-V) that the greater the amount of sodium aquopentacyanoferrite used, the greater is the rate. But it is observed (Tables VI and VII) that whatever be the time of exposure (2 min. or 5 min.) the same rate is obtained when $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ is mixed with H_2O_2 in the dark after insolation. This suggests that by exposing a solution of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ of a particular strength (in this case $M/32.10$) the same amount of aquoferrite is produced irrespective of the duration of exposure, otherwise the velocity constants should have been different. This can only be accounted for by the existence of an equilibrium as in (i). Also the above equilibrium is reversible in the dark, as shown by Table VII.

A proof in support of the above mechanism is found in the fact that the end-solution in all the above experiments containing illuminated $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ gives a greenish colouration with dilute HCl, proving thereby the presence

of aquoferrite. This proves that potassium aquopentacyanoferrite remains unchanged in the presence of excess of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, whereas in the absence of the latter it is completely converted to ferrate. The violet colour of aquopentacyanoferrate is discharged by $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ with the result that the aquopentacyanoferrite of yellow colour is again produced with the simultaneous formation of $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ as shown in equation (iii).

CONCLUSION.

When a solution of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ is illuminated by bright sunlight, a photochemical equilibrium is set up with the production of potassium aquopentacyanoferrite upto a maximum concentration. The latter decomposes H_2O_2 and the rate is maintained at the high value till the end of the reaction. But when a reaction mixture, $K_4Fe(CN)_6 + H_2O_2$, is exposed to sunlight, the aquo-salt produced is immediately removed from the field of reaction by H_2O_2 , and the photochemical equilibrium is shifted to the right with the additional production of aquo-salt which again reacts with H_2O_2 . On the whole, therefore, a greater concentration of the aquo-salt is available when a mixture of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and H_2O_2 is exposed to sunlight than when $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ alone is exposed and the greater concentration of the above substance is responsible for higher value of K .

The cause of the after-effect known in the decomposition of H_2O_2 by $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ after exposure has been found to be due to the reversible photoformation of potassium aquopentacyanoferrite which decomposes H_2O_2 in the dark with a uniformly high velocity, in the presence of excess of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$. The after-effect is not due to the formation of colloidal ferric hydroxide or ferric ion.

The aquopentacyanoferrite is more active in presence of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ than without it, which is proved to be due to the oxidation of ferrite to ferrate by H_2O_2 , and the reduction of ferrate to ferrite by the excess of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$.

A solution of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, exposed to sunlight either for 2 or 5 minutes gives the same value of K with H_2O_2 in the dark. This value is very much higher than that obtained in blanks.

The greater the time of exposure of the mixture, $K_4Fe(CN)_6 - H_2O_2$, the greater is the value of the velocity constant.

A solution of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ exposed to sunlight for 2 or 5 minutes, and then kept in the dark for 10-20 minutes, does not give the same high value of K ,

as is obtained with $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ solution exposed and at once used with H_2O_2 . Hence the production of aquoferrite from $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ by light is a reversible reaction in the dark.

A pre illuminated solution of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ which has been kept in the dark for some minutes and then used gives a slightly lower value of K in the initial stages and it tends to rise in the end.

According to the second part of the suggested mechanism, the main cause of the fast disappearance of H_2O_2 is the decomposition and not its power of oxidation. This fact is corroborated by the violent evolution of oxygen during the reaction.

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